

**University of Belgrade
Faculty of Agriculture**

The 3rd International UNIFood Conference
UNIFood2024 Conference

Book of Abstracts

UNIFOOD

Belgrade, June 28-29, 2024.

UNIFood2024 Conference - Book of Abstract

The 3rd International UNIFood Conference – UNIFood2024

Publisher

University of Belgrade - Faculty of Agriculture
6 Nemanjina street
11080 Zemun - Belgrade

For Publisher

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University of Belgrade
Faculty of Agriculture

Editors

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Cover Design Layout, technical preparation, typesetting

Ivana Isaković

Print run

20 copies

Printing house

Faculty of Agriculture, Nemanjina 6, 11080 Belgrade

ISBN: 978-86-7834-438-1

Belgrade, 2024.

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UNIFood2024 Conference
28th-29th June 2024 University of Belgrade
3rd International UNIFood Conference

CIP - Каталогизација у публикацији Народна библиотека Србије, Београд

663/664(048)

INTERNATIONAL UNIFood Conference (3 ; 2024 ; Beograd)

Book of Abstracts : The 3rd International UNIFood Conference, UNIFood2024 Conference, Belgrade, June 28-29, 2024. / [editors Mirjana Pešić, Slađana Stanojević].
- Belgrade : University, Faculty of Agriculture, 2024 (Beograd : Faculty of Agriculture).
- 165 str. ; 30 cm

Tiraž 20.

ISBN 978-86-7834-438-1

a) Храна -- Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 147592713

HERBS AND SPICES SPICED WITH ALKALOIDS – OVERVIEW OF RASFF NOTIFICATIONS

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Herbs and spices have a long tradition of use in both home and industrial food preparation, aimed at enhancing the sensory characteristics of food. The aim of this study was to observe the occurrence of natural toxins (pyrrolizidine and tropane alkaloids) in herbs and spices. The data originate from the RASFF (**Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed**) database, whose primary objective is to facilitate the exchange of information, thereby enabling timely responses by relevant authorities in case of risks to public health associated with food. The period from 2010 to 2023 was monitored for the type "food", category "herbs and spices" during which 132 notifications were identified. It is noteworthy that no notifications were reported until 2018, attributed to the insufficient capacity of laboratory testing for natural toxins before (the announcement of) their inclusion in Regulation on maximum levels of contaminants in food. The majority of notifications result from official controls on the market (in 67 cases), while a smaller number originate from border controls (36 consignments) and the company's own check (29 cases). Only 6 notifications identified tropane alkaloids, while the remaining 126 were related to pyrrolizidine ones, present in exceptionally variable concentrations, reaching up to 150 mg/kg. In most cases, the raw materials originate from Turkey, and the predominant spices contaminated with pyrrolizidine alkaloids were oregano (approximately 42%) and cumin (approximately 40%) while the remaining 8% of notifications were related to more than 15 types of herbs and spices, including raspberry leaves, parsley and peppermint contaminated with tropane alkaloids. One-half of notifications has been classified as alerts. The risk decision for as much as 120 notifications has been assessed as serious. Considering that pyrrolizidine alkaloids are hepatotoxic and several of them (*lasiocarpine*, *monocrotaline* and *riddelliine*) are classified as possible human carcinogens, their presence in food is highly undesirable.

Keywords: pyrrolizidine alkaloids, tropane alkaloids, food safety, public health